

PSYCHOLOGY OF STORIES AND NOVELS OF ULUG‘BEK HAMDAM

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses one of the most important topics of modern literature - the concept of artistic psychology and its history. As an introduction to the concept, theoretical views of literary scholars and definitions of the term by Uzbek scholars are given.

Key words: *psychology, social consciousness, life reality, modernism, realism, character, concept.*

Introduction. A work of art is a product of the artist's thinking, in which the life of man and society, his destiny and destiny find their image. In every works of art, the events that have happened or may happen in our lives are conveyed by the author to the reader based on the laws of art continues to form. The problems raised in the works of art, the issues referred to the reader's attention and judgment - the theme and content of the work of art are closely related to the social environment when the work was created. In order to deeply and completely reveal the character of the artistic image in the work, the author used the means of artistic imagery as well as the means of psychological imagery. In the work, the author goes deep into the inner world of the

hero, describes the mental world of the character in detail depicts, the feelings of the soul - it is called "artistic psychology".

In scientific sources related to literary studies, three main principles of artistic psychology are distinguished - dynamic principle, analytical principle and typological principle. In the dynamic principle, the psyche of the hero is expressed through his actions, facial expressions and actions, his behavior in various life situations and his words, "in essence, this is similar to the way of revealing the psyche of the characters of a dramatic work, therefore the dynamic principle is sometimes It is defined as the dramaturgy of psychological analysis. In the typological principle, the spirit of the image is described in connection with the conditions of the environment that formed and surrounded it. The analytical principle describes the heroic experiences, feelings in the heart, thinking and reflection, dynamics of thoughts grows, they complement each other, change their quality." This form allows you to show sharp turns in the fate and thinking of the characters. It should be noted that the author can use the above-mentioned three forms together and complement each other to reveal the character of the artistic image and its psyche. If one of the principles is the leader, the other two serve to complement it. In general, the concept of "character" occupies a leading place in researches related to artistic psychology. The reason is that, although research in this direction is related to the science of literary studies, on the one hand, it is directly related to the science of psychology, and is based on the intersection of these two fields. This, in turn, requires clarifying the concept of "character" from the point of view of both literary studies and psychology. only then can it be the achievement of the work. When a writer creates a character, he can directly or indirectly reveal his psyche. The description of the character's home experiences and feelings in the form of "inner monologue", "stream of consciousness" or from the author's language (the author's own speech) is considered a direct form of psychological image. In the work, revealing the psyche of the character by showing his actions, words, facial expressions (mimicry), physiological changes in him is an indirect psychological image. These two types of mental image complement each other, therefore, when describing the psyche

of a certain character, the writer uses both of them effectively. There is a relationship between the concept of artistic psychology and concepts such as psychological analysis or psychological image, which creates controversial situations between scientists and researchers. But these questions remain theoretically open to this day - some researchers clarify these terms, while other groups of scientists try to avoid this theory. In this, the writer reveals his inner world and psychology through his style. In it, the writer reveals the inner world of the hero using the means of psychological images such as internal monologue, speech characterization, psychological portrait, hallucination, dream. In this case, the writer turns to the outside world only to illuminate his inner world.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Among the representatives of Uzbek literature today, Ulugbek Hamdam is one of the writers who have become popular with his deep novels and stories. His novels such as "Muvozanat", "Isyon va Itoat", "Sabo va Samandar" and the collection of short stories and short stories "Uzoqdagi Dilnura" have their place in the Uzbek literature of the 20th century. In addition, poetry collections "Tangriga eltuvchi isyon", "Atirgul" and "Seni kutdim", monographs "Badiiy tafakkur tadriji", "Yangilanish ehtiyoji", "Yangi o'zbek she'riyati" were also published. Among modern Uzbek writers, Ulugbek Hamdam is one of the few creators whose works are often translated into other languages and recognized outside Uzbekistan. His novel "Isyon va Itoat", short story "Yolg'izlik", about ten stories and poems were translated into Russian. The author's story "Tosh" and several poems were translated into English. The novel "Muvoznat" and the story "Tosh" were recognized in America. Ulugbek Hamdam's work is full of novelty and updates. Literary scholars and critics also acknowledge this. The writer's novel "Muvozanat", which has recently entered the literature and is liked by both young and old readers, was announced, and every critic and scholar of literature could not help but react to it. Ulugbek Hamdam penned the situation that was tormenting many people at the time when the novel was written, and which had passed or was passing in the minds of many people. Dilmurod Quronov explains this situation

as follows: " Muvozanat " was born as a novel that was very relevant in terms of the topic and was written at the time. The second side of the issue is how the current topic is covered. The novel is largely autobiographical. Ulug‘bek wrote many parts of the work while crying, pouring his heart and soul into the text. Ulug‘bek Hamdam’s novel "Muvozanat " describes a situation that many people are going through or are going through. " Muvozanat "describes the state of imbalance in our recent past, when changes in our habitual lifestyle caused sharp changes in our psyche. The work is devoted to a very topical problem. The theme chosen in the novel "Muvozanat", the idea of the work can be felt from the name of the novel. In the novel, the criterion in the heart of a person standing on the threshold of a new era is widely covered, due to changes in the social system, time and place, the maintained balance is disturbed to a certain extent. In fact, the theme is new in the novel. The author was able to approach the concept of balance in artistic creation in a new way. "So, it’s not about realism or modernism here. It’s about the artist, his thinking and skills. And in order for a literary work to be an example of a true work, whether it belongs to realism, is written in the style of romanticism, or adheres to some other modernist style, it is necessary to repeat again and again that the human condition is at the center of it. the reader should be able to get some information about the fate, nature, and life of a person, as well as get aesthetic pleasure from this work. The concept of balance, which seems simple at first glance, acquires a very large and extensive essence during the work. He shows his height in every aspect of marriage, life, human spirituality. In the work, the writer connects the same concept with the main idea and theme of the work as the main criterion in illuminating the period and environment after the independence. The composition and plot of the work is also based on this.

At the center of the balance is a person, Yusuf’s fate, his suffering no one denies that their search is on. The work of the student of "Muvozanat" is artistic he sees his reality through the eyes of the author, living in it together with the heroes sees, feels; together with the writer, their fate, mutual relations discusses, tries to understand the root of tragedies, problems looks for a solution and comes to certain conclusions. All

this is aesthetic pleasure. That is, aesthetic pleasure is not a self-manifesting objective property of the work rather it's a spiritual and spiritual process that takes place in the mind and heart of the student. That's why the phenomenon of art exists only in the process of reading, it is always a writer, a work, a reader appears in unity. So, the creation of an artistic event is a work not only to himself, but to the student, his creative imagination, general knowledge and to a number of factors such as cultural level, reading skills, emotional state, intention depend. Based on the description of the author's characters' life paths tried to reveal that period. From the beginning to the end of the novel, Yusuf fought for one thing - for the highest value. "He can give what has happened in life and around him

be that as it may, he did not turn his back on the highest value that holds a person - balance, and the difficulty of achieving it. But it wasn't just a balance. One root of this balance starts from the person himself and the other surely he drinks water from the bosom of the society where he lives. Well, that's it. So the issue of independence and prosperity of the country was meant by Yusuf and the novel itself they are inseparable links of the great Balance, which is sought from the beginning to the end", says Marhabo Kochkarova. Yusuf studied at the university with one goal, after that he worked at the university. He followed only the honest way and supported his family with his monthly salary. But it was difficult to make a living with this money in the city. Difficulty in life showed its effect more and more. Moving from house to house, financial difficulties caused his relationship with Oygul to take a sharp turn. No matter how successful the family is, the union, financial hardship still has its effect. In between, the balance weakens. He loses his balance when he loses his son. The image of Yusuf is a nationalist, a patriot, a person with a high spirit. The historian Muhammadjon in the novel is the image of a man whose era has passed. He realizes that his life is built on a false foundation. That's why he leaves with his eyes open. When the birds are released from the cage, they give symbolic hints to the will of man. While releasing his beloved birds, Mr. Muhammadjon said: "There are no gardens left here, mountains too. They destroyed everything and turned it into a cotton farm! Go,

my bird, three, now, three!" The spirit of the age affects human experiences and man realizes what he has done by fighting with himself. Amir, the biggest and most impressive character in the work, is a typical person of the present past. Although Amir is healthy in spirit and body, he is thrown into a madhouse. Amir is forced to drive himself crazy while being healthy. Symbolically, he sees himself in the form of a feather plucked by the hands of madmen. Amir himself Unsatisfied desires after not being able to achieve your dreams in your life dream life, unrequited love - left their mark on his future destiny. The reader cannot indifferently read the images related to the image of Amir without mental torture and unrestrained questions.

Conclusion. Looking at the history of the issue of artistic psychology within the framework uzbek literary studies, we can see that the scientific research that should be carried out on this issue in uzbek literary studies is relevant and necessary today. The problem of artistic psychology has been studied in more detail in the scientific researches of uzbek literary scholars-scientists, and their views on this theory have been revealed in detail. Among the samples of modern literature, which world literary processes are rapidly developing, growing and changing day by day, the research and study of prose genres such as psychological novel, psychological short story and psychological story within the framework of the literature of each nation is one of the urgent issues facing today's science. With his novel "Muvozanat", Ulug'bek Hamdam fully proved that it is possible to express new artistic and aesthetic thinking in uzbek literature of the 20th century with traditionalism. Especially, the image of Amir in the work entered the Uzbek literature as a completely new symbol. It became clear that there are undiscovered aspects and problems of literature in discovering a person through his means. It can be concluded from the work that if the whole universe is based on the law of balance, then society and the people who form its foundation are stable because of the same balance. As soon as the balance is disturbed in life, then all kinds of unexpected changes and even derailments begin among its members. When we read not only novels, but also short stories of the writer, we see that he has fully demonstrated his writing skills, portraying the heroes of the work and the spirit of the

time in true ways. Deep scientific research of Ulug‘bek Hamdam’s work provides new information for the science of literary studies. Therefore, increasing research in this regard is not without benefit.

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